

Aanvraag**Financiering****Titel**

The Sharing Economy: Societal Implications of Online Streaming

Aanvrager

Uw weerwoord is in bewerking

Dr. H. Datta

Referentenrapport van referent 1**Assessment of the quality of the researcher.****Toelichting**

Criteria - Quality of the researcher - in terms of profile fit in the target group; - from an international perspective belongs to the 10 to 20% of his/her peer group; - academic excellence as demonstrated by the PhD thesis, publications and/or other relevant achievements in the field; - inspiring enthusiasm for research and/or technology; - persuasiveness; - clear indications of an outstanding talent for academic research. The Veni scheme aims at outstanding researchers only: the top 10-20% of his/her international peer group.

Vraag a

a

What is your opinion on the past performance of the researcher (as demonstrated by his/her doctoral thesis, publications, and other relevant scientific achievements)?

Commentaar

The researcher defended his PhD dissertation in 2013 and already has one publication in Journal of Marketing Research, which is one of the 5 top journals in marketing. This is quite impressive. He also seems to have a number of interesting papers in the pipe-line. He therefore seems to be at start of a promising research career.

Vraag b

b

Does the applicant belong to the top 10-20% of his/her international peer group? Which scientific achievements or talents of the applicant show he/she belongs to this top?

Commentaar

I am not really in a position to judge as I am not working in the field of marketing. However, as indicated above, managing to publish a paper in a top journal at this early stage of a career shows that the researcher is not far from the top of his peer group.

Assessment of the quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposal

Toelichting

Criteria - Quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposed research - challenging in terms of content; - originality of the research topic; - innovative scientific elements; - potential to make an important contribution to science; - effective in terms of proposed methodology.

Vraag a

a

Please comment on the relevance of the problem and on the originality and challenging content of the proposal.

Commentaar

The problem is extremely relevant. The demand- and supply-side effects of the streaming of information goods are largely unascertained. On the one hand, it is important to know better if and how consumption patterns change when streaming replaces ownership; on the other hand, a better knowledge of demand is essential to understand how supply decisions may also be affected by the transition from ownership to streaming. These issues are important not only for the stakeholders (artists, producers of content, platform operators) but also for regulators (for instance, the issue of switching costs across streaming platforms is key to analyze competition in this market).

Vraag b

b

What are the innovative aspects of the proposal? Will the research break new ground by generating new concepts, a deeper understanding, new methods, etc.?

Commentaar

As written above, this research is likely to bring a deeper understanding of a number of important issues related to the streaming of information goods. This understanding will prove valuable for all stakeholders and also for scholars interested in these issues. As far as I can judge, the methods that the researcher plan to use to analyze his data are state-of-the art (by the way, the data sets that the researcher have put together are an innovative aspect of the proposal by themselves).

Vraag c

c

What is your opinion on its potential to make a major contribution to the advancement of scholarship, science or technology (academic impact)?

Commentaar

Given the researcher's potential and the excellent research environment he will be working in, I have high hopes in the academic impact of this research proposal. I am certainly very curious to read the results of this research and I am certain that many scholars working in the fields of the economics and management of content industries will share my curiosity.

Vraag d

d

To what extent is the proposed method effective? Please comment.

Commentaar

As far as I can judge, yes.

Assessment of the knowledge utilisation

Toelichting

Criteria - Knowledge utilisation (= KU)
NWO uses a broad definition of KU: not only innovative end of pipe product creation is considered, but also purposeful interaction with (potential) knowledge users, such as industry or public organisations and knowledge transfer to other scientific disciplines. NWO asks applicants to fill out the paragraph on KU. An applicant may however explain that KU cannot be expected given the nature of the research project. In that case, we still kindly ask you to assess whether the applicant has provided reasonable argument or evidence sufficiently.

Potential - contribution to society and/or other academic areas; - disciplines and organisations that might benefit from the results.

Implementation - action plan to allow the outcomes of the research project to benefit the potential knowledge users; - if and how the potential knowledge users will be involved; - (concrete) outcomes for society; - the period over which KU is expected to occur.

Vraag a

a

What is your opinion on the described relevance of the results of the research?

Commentaar

I have already indicated above that the research proposal has the potential to interest all stakeholders in content industries, as well as regulators. The research proposal addresses a number of topical questions for which sound empirical evidence is currently lacking. This is also an area where there is a lot of public attention and public debate. I am therefore convinced that the researcher will disseminate his results outside academic circles very easily through a clever use of social media (Twitter and the like).

Vraag b

b

Please comment on the effectiveness and feasibility of the proposed approach for knowledge utilisation.

Commentaar

The dissemination strategy that the researcher intends to follow seems a bit ambitious: setting up meetings with an industry audience, talking to journalists, ... are time-consuming activities (even if, I imagine, the researcher will benefit from the support of his university in these matters). Yet, as written above, a clever use of social media may be a more efficient way of disseminating knowledge related to the project.

Vraag c

c

Only answer this question in case the applicant argued that knowledge utilisation is not to be expected given the nature of the research proposal: Does the applicant convincingly explain why knowledge utilization is not applicable for his/her research project (see also the information under criterion 3 listed above)?

Commentaar

n.a.

Final assessment

Vraag a

a

How do you assess the entire application? Please give your final scoring (A+/A/B/UF/U).

Referentcommentaar

02, A High quality, significance and recommendation for funding

Vraag b

b

Could you please summarize (point by point) on the strengths and weaknesses of the grant application focussing on the candidate, proposal and knowledge utilization?

Commentaar

+: high relevance, topical, nice data sets, high quality researcher and research environment
-: project may be a little too ambitious both in terms of results to be achieved and in terms of knowledge diffusion

Referentenrapport van referent 2

Assessment of the quality of the researcher.

Toelichting

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Vraag a

a

What is your opinion on the past performance of the researcher (as demonstrated by his/her doctoral thesis, publications, and other relevant scientific achievements)?

Commentaar

The main publication of the candidate is co-authored senior researchers. There is no evidence that the candidate can successfully complete a complex structural dynamic econometrics project without senior researchers.

Vraag b

b

Does the applicant belong to the top 10-20% of his/her international peer group? Which scientific achievements or talents of the applicant show he/she belongs to this top?

Commentaar

It is hard to assess the rank of the candidate as there is only one publication with senior co-authors after 3 years of being assistant professor. There are no other submitted work or work under revision for a journal.

Assessment of the quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposal

Toelichting

Criteria - Quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposed research - challenging in terms of content; - originality of the research topic; - innovative scientific elements; - potential to make an important contribution to science; - effective in terms of proposed methodology.

Vraag a

a

Please comment on the relevance of the problem and on the originality and challenging content of the proposal.

Commentaar

The question of the impact of digital technologies on markets and on consumer behaviors is important.

Vraag b

b

What are the innovative aspects of the proposal? Will the research break new ground by generating new concepts, a deeper understanding, new methods, etc.?

Commentaar

The author does not propose a structural econometric approach. Rather, it seems to me that the approach is purely empirical with some insights from theory (the project description is too vague to correctly assess the methodology used).

Vraag c

c

What is your opinion on its potential to make a major contribution to the advancement of scholarship, science or technology (academic impact)?

Commentaar

There are several key recent theoretical and empirical papers missing from the literature; the candidate should make clear that he is not addressing the issues of uber/Airbnb/etc, which are more what people have in mind when they talk about the sharing economy. Streaming per se does not imply sharing.

Vraag d

d

To what extent is the proposed method effective? Please comment.

Commentaar

The author has little experience on the study of digital markets. Potential collaborations with other researchers in the field should be highlighted.

Assessment of the knowledge utilisation

Toelichting

Criteria - Knowledge utilisation (= KU)
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Potential - contribution to society and/or other academic areas; - disciplines and organisations that might benefit from the results.

Implementation - action plan to allow the outcomes of the research project to benefit the potential knowledge users; - if and how the potential knowledge users will be involved; - (concrete) outcomes for society; - the period over which KU is expected to occur.

Vraag a

a

What is your opinion on the described relevance of the results of the research?

Commentaar

Research is highly relevant for knowledge utilization. The technical feasibility of the econometric project is questionable.

Vraag b

b

Please comment on the effectiveness and feasibility of the proposed approach for knowledge utilisation.

Commentaar

See previous point. I am not sure what the candidate has in mind when he talks about the sharing economy.

Vraag c

c

Only answer this question in case the applicant argued that knowledge utilisation is not to be expected given the nature of the research proposal: Does the applicant convincingly explain why knowledge utilization is not applicable for his/her research project (see also the information under criterion 3 listed above)?

Commentaar

N/A

Final assessment

Vraag a

a

How do you assess the entire application? Please give your final scoring (A+/A/B/UF/U).

Referentcommentaar

04, UF Good, but unsuccessful in this form

Vraag b

b

Could you please summarize (point by point) on the strengths and weaknesses of the grant application focussing on the candidate, proposal and knowledge utilization?

Commentaar

1. Artists do not benefit from streaming revenues, especially musicians (other than the main artist). It is important to model the role of intermediaries, such as music label.
2. The debate about owning vs. renting concerns durable goods. The author does not mention the feature of digital goods that has implications in terms of intertemporal price discrimination
3. Please explain the main contributions to the academic literature. Please cite recent relevant such as T P Thomes. An economic analysis of online streaming music services. Information Economics and Policy 25, 81-91 (2013). Please also cite the huge literature on switching costs.
4. The author should consider the impact of complementary markets such as live concerts and merchandizing on the economic trade-offs between platforms and artists
5. The author should be more specific about the econometric model and the methodology that will be used to estimate dynamic simultaneous equations. The author should also provide evidence that he will be able to carry the estimation phase within a reasonable timeframe.
6. In the budget sheet, it is not clear how the salary will be split between the home institution and the grant (items 3.c and 3.d). This should be clarified upfront.

Overall

Overall weerwoord

Maximum aantal woorden voor de toelichting over alle referentenrapporten 1000

Afzien van weerwoord false